

Review Article

A Review On Phytochemical Constituents And Medicinal Values Of “*Cheilocostus Speciosus*”

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ABSTRACT

Cheilocostus Speciosus is a plant in the family Asteraceae It is widespread to Southeast Asia and adjacent regions, ranging from India to China to Queensland. It is particularly prevalent on Indonesia's Greater Sunda Islands. Puerto Rico, Mauritius, Reunion, Fiji, Hawaii, Costa Rica, Belize, Melanesia, Micronesia, and the West Indies are also said to have naturalised. This review includes the Plant profile, major constituents, Chemical test, and the pharmacological activities of *Cheilocostus Speciosus*. The main constituents of the plant were diosgenin, curcumin, and curcuminoids. Costus tubers and roots include 5-stigmasten-3b-ol, sitosterol--D-glucoside, dioscin, prosapogenins A and B of dioscin, gracillin and quinines. Saponins have also been reported from rhizomes, including seeds and roots. Which shows pharmacological active effects such as *Cheilocostus Speciosus*, Anticancer activity, Anti-inflammatory, Anti-diabetic activity, Antimicrobial activity, and others. The rhizome extract is used as a tonic and is beneficial in the treatment of burning sensations, constipation, leprosy, asthma, bronchitis, anaemia, and various skin problems. Costus rhizomes are used as a herbal fever treatment.

INTRODUCTION

Many countries of the world, including India, are rapidly losing traditional knowledge of herbal medicines for treating human ailments. Nowadays, tribals and indigenous groups in India use herbal medicine to treat a wide range of ailments and disorders. They collect and preserve plant species that are locally available, wild, or cultivated. The

research area has no prior records of ethnomedical knowledge. As a result, an effort has been made to chronicle plant species, medicinal formulations, and disease treatment by various communities living in this area[1]. *Speciosus* is among the most effective Islamic traditional medicinal plants[2]. *Cheilocostus speciosus*, or crêpe ginger, is a species of flowering plant in the family Costaceae.

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It is widespread to Southeast Asia and adjacent regions, ranging from India to China to Queensland. It is particularly prevalent on Indonesia's Greater Sunda Islands. Puerto Rico, Mauritius, Réunion, Fiji, Hawaii, Costa Rica, Belize, Melanesia, Micronesia, and the West Indies are also said to have naturalised. It is extensively grown as an ornamental[3]. These plants have been known to demonstrate pharmacological activities such as anti-inflammatory, anti-microbial, antioxidant, anti-dyslipidemic and anti-cancer. The plant is also recognised to be abundant in antioxidants such as ascorbic acid, carotene, tocopherol, glutathione, phenol, and flavonoids. The seeds include two novel quinones, di-hydrophytic plastoquinone and its methyl derivatives, as well as tocopherol[4].

Plant profile:

Cheilocostus speciosus, is a species of flowering plant in the family Costaceae

Vernacular names:

Assam	Tara
Bengali	Keu, Keumut
Kannada	Changalvakostu, Chikke
Malayalam	Channakoova
Marathi	Penva, Pinnha, Kobee, Peva
Tamil	Kostam
Sanskrit	Kembuka, Kebuka, Kembu
Telegu	Kashmeeramu, Cengalvakostu
Classical name	Kebuka
English	Crepe ginger
Guajarati	Paskarmula, Valakdi

Hindi	Keu, Keukand, Kemuka, Kemua
Latin name	Costus speciosus

Taxonomical classification:

Kingdom	Plantae
Sub-kingdom	Tracheobionta
Super division	Spermatophyta
Division	Magnoliophyta
Class	Liliopsida
Sub-class	Zingiberidae
Order	Zingiberales
Family	Costaceae
Genus	Costus
species	Speciosus

[FIGs: Plant phenotypes of *Costus speciosus*: a) growing plantlet; b) young plant at initial developmental stage; c) small plant with young leaves; d) plant showing vegetative stage; e-h) flowering stages; i) plants bearing flowers in dense vegetation; j) single plant showing all plant parts; k) plant rhizome with small peripheral roots.]

DISTRIBUTION:

Costus speciosus is a species native to Southeast Asia's Malay Peninsula. The plant naturally occurs in the Sub-Himalayan region, sections of central India, and the Western Ghats of Maharashtra and Karnataka in addition to Kerala [5]. The *Costus* genus contains around 100 different species. Flower colour varies between *Costus* species. Some flower and bract kinds resemble compact cones, whilst others resemble pineapples or soft crepes emerging from green cones. India is home to approximately seven species of the genus *Costus* Linn. *C. barbatus*, *C. chartaceus*, *C. cuspidatus*, *C. giganteus*, *C. igneus*, *C. osae*, and *C. spectabilis* are other cultivated species of this genus.

CHEMICAL CONSTITUENTS:

The rhizomes are the primary source of diosgenin. The main chemical ingredients are diosgenin, curcumin, and curcuminoids. *Costus* tubers and roots include 5-stigmasten-3 β -ol, sitosterol--D-

glucoside, dioscin, prosapogenins A and B of dioscin, gracillin, and quinines [6]. Saponins have also been reported from rhizomes, including seeds and roots. Saponins extracted from seeds have been reported to have hypotensive and spasmolytic properties. Tigogenin and diosgenin (2.6%) have been isolated from rhizomes [7]. Various chemicals such as -amyrinsterate, -amyrin, and lupeol Palmitates were isolated from the leaves [8]. Two novel quinones, dihydrophytylplastoquinone and its 6-methyl derivatives, and tocopherol were isolated from seeds [9]. Tetradecyl 13-methylpentadecanoate, tetradecyl 11-methyltridecanoate, 14-oxotricosanoic acid, 14-oxoheptacosanoic acid, and 15-oxooctacosanoic acid have been isolated from rhizomes [10]. Palmitic acid (55.97%), oleic acid (23.75%), linoleic, stearic, myristic, and lauric acids are all present in seed oil (6.0%). Defatted seeds included diosgenin, glucose, galactose, and rhamnose. The roots yielded 31-norcycloartanone, cycloartanol,

cycloartenol, and cyclolaudenol[11]. Methyl 3-(4-hydroxyphenyl)-2E propenoate was extracted from rhizomes [12].

CULTIVATION

C. speciosus is typically grown on fertile, organic, wet, well-drained soils in the shade [13]. It grows best in tropical climates with high humidity and minimum temperatures of 13o C. The thick fleshy roots known as "rhizomes" are the source of pancake ginger's growth. Under optimal growing conditions, a single rhizome can produce new shoots and grow to form a 3 ft broad clump in the second year. *Costus* reproduces naturally by rhizomes, culm division, and stem cuttings. It can also be cultivated from seeds. Birds share *costus* seeds as they feast on the fruits.

MEDICINAL PROPERTIES

The bitter rhizomes have anthelmintic, astringent, and expectorant effects. [14] [15] [16] .mThe rhizome extract is used as a tonic and is beneficial in the treatment of burning sensations,

constipation, leprosy, asthma, bronchitis, anaemia, and various skin problems [17]. *Costus* rhizomes are used as a herbal fever treatment. *C.speciosus* rhizome exhibits hepatoprotective effects [18]. Rhizome paste is used to cure boils as well as to manufacture sexual hormones and contraceptives [19]. Scabies and stomach disorders are treated with the leaves. Stems are ground into a paste and used to treat blisters.Snake bites are treated using rhizome extract. [20] [21] [22].*C.speciosus* has been used as a medical herb for centuries, primarily for its stimulant, carminative, diuretic, digestive, and antibacterial characteristics.

OTHER USES

Southeast Asia *C. speciosus* is a food plant. Vegetables include tender young branches, fruits, and rhizome.

PHARMACOLOGY

It contains several different kinds of*C. speciosus* activities. A figure depicts several activities.

Anticancer activity:

C. speciosus preparations in methanol and ethyl acetate shown antitumor activity. Baskar et al. (2012) discovered that *C. speciosus* had antioxidant and antiproliferative properties against a human colon cancer cell line (COLO 320DM).

Costunolide was discovered to be involved in the arrest of human breast cancer (MDA-MB-231) cells at the G2/M phase of the cell cycle. Another chemical, diosgenin, has been shown to suppress the growth of hepatocellular carcinoma (HepG2) cells.[23]

Anti-inflammatory:

Using adult albino rats and Swiss albino mice, methanolic extracts of aerial portions of *Costus speciosus* (400 and 800 mg/kg BW) shown anti-inflammatory, analgesic, and antipyretic effects (Srivastava et al., 2013). The anti-inflammatory efficacy of methanol extract was tested on rats using the carrageenan-induced paw oedema test. The analgesic effect of *C. speciosus* on mice was also investigated using acetic acid-induced writhing and Eddy's hot plate methods. This plant's antipyretic activity was tested in rats using Brewer's yeast-induced pyrexia (Srivastava et al., 2013).[24]

Anti-diabetic activity:

Diabetes mellitus is associated with low insulin levels in the blood, and low insulin levels in the blood induce coronary artery disease, cerebrovascular illness, renal failure, and blindness, all of which can lead to premature death. *Costus speciosus* is also known as the 'insulin plant' (Daisy et al., 2008)[25], and diosgenin, which is found in the rhizome of *C. speciosus*, has been utilised as an anti-diabetic medication (Raniet et al., 2012; Sulakshana and Rani, 2014)[26]. An experiment was carried out with petroleum ether, chloroform, methanolic, and aqueous extracts of *C. speciosus* rhizome to validate the antidiabetic potential. In rats, the extracts (50 mg/kg BW intraperitoneal and 0.6 mg/kg BW glibenclamide, orally) demonstrated promising anti-diabetic activity (Bavarva and Narasimhacharya, 2008; Rajesh et al., 2009; Ali et al., 2014).[27]

Antimicrobial activity:

Oral administration of antibiotic compounds may result in undesirable side effects; for example, oral administration of penicillin may cause heartburn, nausea, vomiting, and diarrhoea. As a result, various trials on herbs and spices as antibiotic substitutes were done.[28]. In comparison to silver sulfadiazine cream, hexane and methanol extracts

of *C. speciosus*. leaf and rhizomes displayed a lysis zone against *Shigella* spp., *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Pseudomonas* spp., *Bacillus subtilis*, and *Salmonella* spp.[29] The antifungal effect of costunolide displayed significant minimal inhibitory concentration values of 62.5 g/ml against *Trichophyton mentagrophytes*, 62.0 g/ml against *Trichophyton simii*, 125 g/ml against *Epidermophyton floccosum*, 31.25 g/ml against *Trichophyton rubrum*, 125 g/ml against *Curvularia lunata*, 62.5 g/ml against *T. rubrum*.

Other activities:

- Hepatoprotective activity.
- Hypolipidemic activity.
- Adaptogenic activity.
- Insecticidal and acaricidal activity.

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE PROSPECTS:

Cheilocostus Speciosus is a medicinal plant with numerous pharmacological qualities, including anticancer and anti-inflammatory activities. Antidiabetic action, antimicrobial activity, and other activities such as hepatoprotective activity, hypolipidemic activity, adaptogenic activity, insecticidal and acaricidal activity are all examples of its properties. As a result, it has the potential to be a beneficial therapeutic agent for the treatment of a variety of disorders.

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